

ISic0300

I.Sicily inscription 0300

Language

Latin

Type

votive

Material

copper

Object

lamina

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Catina

Place of origin (modern)

Catania

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Catania

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. Annia · Zosima

2. votum

3. lucernam

Apparatus

Text of CIL

Translation (en)

Annia Zosima (dedicated this?) lamp as an offering.

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 491511

EDR 141136

EDCS 21900335

Bibliography

Mommsen, Th. 1883. Inscriptiones Bruttiorum Lucaniae Campaniae Siciliae Sardiniae Latinae. Pars posterior. Inscriptiones Siciliae et Sardiniae. *Corpus Inscriptionum Latinarum, consilio et auctoritate Academiae Litterarum Regiae Borussicae editum*. Berlin. At 10.7016 (<http://arachne.uni-koeln.de/item/buchseite/650756>)

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